

THE PLACE OF THE DIGITAL ECONOMY TODAY

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Abstract: This article analyzes the emergence of the digital economy, what the digital economy is, the importance of digital technologies in the world economy and society, the advantages and disadvantages of the digital economy.

Keywords: Digital economy, Technology, Information security, Digital technology, Robotics.

Today, the development of the digital economy is one of the unique features of the 21st century. Digital technologies affect society and economy in many ways. In recent years, a new wave of development in business and social sphere activities is taking place with the help of a new generation of digital technologies, i.e. artificial intelligence, robotics, and wireless communication technologies. The development of the digital economy is one of the priorities for the USA, Great Britain, Germany, Japan, Switzerland, France, Russia and other leading countries. The concept of digital economy was not long ago, that is, it was first used by a Japanese professor in the 1990s during the Japanese crisis. In 1995, it was defined by Nicholas Negroponte, an American scientist from the University of Massachusetts. The scientist mentioned what changes may occur during the transition from the old economy to the new economy following the intensive development of information and communication technologies. First of all, what is the digital economy? the question can be answered as follows. The digital economy is an economic activity in which the main factor in production and service is information in the form of numbers, with the help of processing a large amount of information and analyzing the result of this processing. is to implement more effective solutions than the previous system in production, service, technologies, devices, storage, product delivery. In other words, the digital economy is an activity connected with the development of digital computer technologies in the provision of online services, electronic payments, internet trade and other types of industries. In our opinion, the digital economy is an economic activity that is implemented and managed with the help of digital technologies in the context of a shortage of economic resources. The

main problem facing any economic system is the scarcity of resources, and the main attention should be focused on solving this problem in the digital economy. The digital economy is used to represent two different concepts. First, the digital economy is considered a modern stage of development, characterized by the priority of creative work and information benefits. Secondly, the digital economy is a unique concept, the object of its study is the information society. Of course, the development of information and communication technologies, the application of modern technologies to our lives can provide many positive opportunities in the life of every person. Following the development of digital technologies, a person can use the service he needs faster, save a lot of money by buying the products he needs cheaply through the Internet. For example, buying a book in electronic form It may cost you much less to buy the same book in printed form. Otherwise, an ordinary consumer can become an entrepreneur himself and engage in online sales without leaving his home.

Other advantages of the development of the digital economy can be as follows:

- increasing labor productivity in production;
- increasing the competitiveness of companies;
- reduction of production costs;
- emergence of new modern professions;
- overcoming poverty and social inequality
- emergence of new forms of work sold through online platforms;
- digital transformation, change of trade infrastructure for special services.

The digital economy brings many conveniences to human life as well as many inconveniences. Problems related to personal data are cyberattacks, job losses due to the development of new technology and robotics, the disappearance of certain types of activities, and other such problems. Among them, the most developed today is a cyber attack. However, it should be noted that the digital economy in Uzbekistan is developing several times slower than the potential of Uzbekistan. That is, there is an opportunity, the necessary resources are available, but the development is rather slow. As a reason for this, a number of obstacles to the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan can be pointed out.

- monopoly in many areas;
- low internet speed and poor quality;

- the fact that legislation in the field of information technologies is behind the times;
- low level of computer literacy among citizens;
- lack of information technology specialists or their departure to other countries;
- information technology security is not good, etc.

To sum up, the digital economy has become today's demand. If the above-mentioned problems are solved gradually, systematically, based on world experience, Uzbekistan can easily become one of the countries with a developed digital economy. It is necessary for us young people to overcome the problems in the digital economy of Uzbekistan by making reasonable use of the current opportunities.

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